
Environment and its influence

Photoperiod sensitivity of Rayada rices

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Rayada, unlike traditional deepwater rice varieties, has cold tolerance at seedling stage, lacks seed dormancy, has a very long growth duration (11 mo), and is cultivated in 3.7-6 m water depth.

The Rayada rices in Bangladesh are sown with boro rices as a mixed crop. Boro varieties are photoperiod insensitive and are usually harvested in Apr or May when Rayada plants are vegetative. Rayada rices continue to grow under subsequent deepwater conditions and do not flower until late Sep and Oct when day length is less than 12 hours, Rayada rices do not respond to short photoperiod in Feb and early Mar when planted in Nov, and always flower in Sep and Oct. Is this group of cultivars a photoperiod-sensitive type with a long basic vegetative phase (BVP)? We tried to verify this assumption.

Five strains of Rayada conserved by the IRRI International Rice Germplasm Center were used. Habiganj (HBJ) aman 1, a deepwater rice variety, was the photoperiod-sensitive check and HBJ boro 5 was the insensitive check. Plants received 10, 12, 14, and 16 h photoperiods starting at seeding dates. Plants that did not flower after 140 days of growth were dissected and checked for panicle primordia.

HBJ aman 1 and Rayada strains flowered at 10 and 12 h photoperiod and re-

Days to flower, basic vegetative phase (BVP) and photoperiod sensitive phase (PSP) of five strains of Rayada, HBJ aman 1, and HBJ boro 5 at different photoperiods.

Variety, strains	Days to flowering ^a at photoperiod of				BVP	PSP
	10 h	12 h	14 h	16 h		
Rayada 16-02	108	126	–	–	73	140+
Rayada 16-03	108	124	–	–	73	140+
Rayada 16-05	109	126	–	–	74	140+
Rayada 16-06	108	124	–	–	13	140+
Rayada 16-08	105	125	–	–	70	140+
HBJ aman 1	38	80	–	–	3	140+
HBJ boro 5	92	92	97	92	57	5

^aA dash (–) means the variety did not initiate panicles after 140 days of growth.

mained vegetative at 14 and 16 h photoperiods (see table). HBJ boro 5 flowered at all the photoperiod treatments, with similar flowering duration. Based on flowering behavior, both HBJ aman 1 and Rayada strains are strongly photoperiod sensitive with a long photoperiod-sensitive phase (PSP) and critical photoperiod of around 12 hours.

The BVP, which is synonymous with insensitive phase or juvenile stage of a variety, can be estimated by subtracting 35 days from the number of days from sowing to flowering when the plants are grown under optimum photoperiod. Although the BVP range reported in the literature varies from 10 to 63 days, none of the strongly photoperiod-sensitive varieties so far tested had a BVP of more than 49 days. Rayada strains had a 70- to 74-day BW.

On the basis of BVP and PSP duration, rice varieties are classified into four types.

Type A has a short BVP and PSP, type B has a long BVP and short PSP, and type C has short BVP and long PSP. Type D varieties with long BVP and PSP have not yet been reported, but present observations indicate Rayadas are type D.

Type D varieties were probably eliminated during domestication because they have an unusually long growth duration. That Rayada rices represent less than 10% of the total deepwater rices in Bangladesh substantiates this statement.

Although the different Rayada strains are strongly photoperiod-sensitive with a BVP of around 70 days and a critical photoperiod of around 12 h, they do not respond to shorter Feb and Mar photoperiods when planted in Nov. Low temperatures in Nov, Dec, and Jan may extend the already long BVP so that when the plant is ready for photoinduction, the day length is already longer than the critical photoperiod.

Rice-based cropping systems

Agroeconomic performance of six rice - wheat cropping patterns, Thakurgaon, Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, 92% of the farmers grow rice on 74% of the cultivable land. Rice is about 93% and wheat is 5% of cereal grains production.

During the 1970s introduction of high yielding rice varieties from BRRI and modern wheat varieties from the Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute dramatically changed agriculture in Bangladesh. High yielding, short-duration,

photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties sometimes perform well in rice - wheat cropping patterns in some wheat-growing areas. Time of transplanted (t.) aman rice harvest, and planting time and growth duration of wheat varieties are critical to this cropping pattern. A late t. aman harvest delays wheat planting, which causes low yield because grain must ripen during hot, dry weather. To attain maximum

production and economic return, appropriate rice and wheat varieties must be selected.

Six rice - wheat cropping patterns were tested at three sites of the North Bangladesh Tubewell Project, Thakurgaon, during 1981-82 and agro-economic analysis was used to determine the most productive, profitable rice - wheat combinations.

BR4, BR10, and Pajam rices yielded more than BR11, Kalam, and Malshara. Pavon wheat yielded more than Balaka, Jupateca, and Sonalika (see table). BR4 - Pavon and Pajam - Pavon rice - wheat combinations yielded more and had higher net return and benefit-cost ratios than BR10 with Balaka and two local

Agroeconomic performance of six rice - wheat cropping patterns. Thakurgaon, Bangladesh, 1981-82.

Cropping pattern			Mean yield (t/ha)		Gross return ^c /pattern (\$/ha)	Net return /pattern (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice		Wheat	Rice	Wheat			
BR4 ^a	—	Pavon	4.4	2.9	1312	792	2.5
BR10 ^a	—	Balaka	3.4	2.3	1027	566	2.2
BR11 ^a	—	Jupateca	3.0	1.6	822	384	1.9
Pajam	—	Pavon	3.8	2.7	1179	666	2.3
Kalam ^b	—	Sonalika	2.3	1.6	708	244	1.5
Malshara ^b	—	Sonalika	1.7	1.4	562	147	1.3

^aHigh-yielding variety. ^bLocal variety. ^cRice price = \$160.74/ton; wheat price = \$207.62/ton.

varieties with Sonalika. Cost of growing local rice varieties generally was low, but low yield potential reduced profits. Local photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties also are harvested late, and delayed planting

of Sonalika wheat, which reduced its yield. With an assured water supply, BR4 - Pavon and Pajam - Pavon can be grown successfully in the Thakurgaon tubewell project. □

Performance of rice-based cropping patterns in the irrigated uplands of Orissa

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Rice, planted on more than 4 million ha, is the major crop in Orissa. We studied the following rice-based cropping at the Bhubaneswar Research Farm in 1981-82:

1. rice (Annapurna) — rice (Jagannath) — rice (Jaya),
2. rice (Annapurna) — groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*, variety AK12-24) — ragi (*Eleusine coracana*, variety Dibyasingh),
3. rice (Jaya) — potato (*Solanum tuberosum*, variety Kufri Sinduri) — sesamum (*Sesamum indicum*, variety B67),
4. rice (Annapurna) — maize (*Zea mays*, variety Jawahar composite) — cowpea (*Vigna sinensis*, variety SEB2),
5. jute (*Corchorus* sp., variety JRC212) — rice (Jagannath) — groundnut (AK12-24), and
6. rice (Jaya) — knolkhol (*Brassica oleracea*, variety Caulorapa) — lady's finger (*Abelmoschus esculantus*, variety Pusa Sawani).

Annapurna was drilled and Jaya was transplanted. There are three crop seasons: kharif (Jul-Oct), rabi (Nov-Feb), and summer (Mar-Jun). In 1981-82 rain-fall was 1,120 mm in kharif, 51 mm in

Duration, grain yield, and total dry matter production of crop patterns in Orissa, India.

Cropping pattern no.	Crop	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)						Total dry wt (t/ha)
			Grain	Straw	Others ^a				
					Edible		Nonedible		
					F	D	F	D	
1	Rice	70	2.9	4.5	—	—	—	—	7.4
	Rice	98	3.9	5.0	—	—	—	—	8.9
	Rice	115	4.6	6.9	—	—	—	—	11.5
	Total	283	11.4	16.4	—	—	—	—	27.8
2	Rice	110	4.3	6.1	—	—	—	—	10.4
	Groundnut	120	—	—	—	2.6	8.2	2.3	4.9
	Ragi	85	2.4	3.5	—	—	—	—	5.9
Total	315	6.7	9.6	—	2.6	8.2	2.3	21.2	
3	Rice	110	4.6	6.8	—	—	—	—	11.4
	Potato	110	—	—	16.8	3.1	15.1	2.5	5.6
	Sesamum	95	0.8	1.6	—	—	4.5	2.1	4.5
Total	315	5.4	8.4	16.8	3.1	19.6	4.6	21.5	
4	Rice	110	4.5	6.7	—	—	—	—	11.2
	Maize	95	3.8	—	—	—	—	5.0	8.8
	Cowpea	80	—	—	3.6	0.5	4.4	0.8	1.3
Total	285	8.3	6.7	3.6	0.5	4.4	5.8	21.3	
5	Jute	132	—	—	—	—	—	3.0 F ^a 4.5 S ^b	7.5
	Rice	100	3.7	5.5	—	—	—	—	9.2
Groundnut	120	—	—	—	—	2.5	—	3.1	5.6
	Total	352	3.1	5.5	—	2.5	—	10.6	22.3
6	Rice	110	4.5	6.6	—	—	—	—	11.1
	Knolkhol	60	—	—	8.3	1.1	5.0	0.8	1.9
	Lady's finger	70	—	—	4.1	0.6	6.7	2.0	2.6
Total	240	4.5	6.6	13.0	1.7	11.7	2.8	15.6	
CD (0.05)									0.68

^aF = fiber, D = dry matter. ^bS = sticks.

rabi, and 306 mm in summer. Kharif rice and jute were rainfed and the rabi and summer crops received irrigation when

necessary.

Of the cropping patterns evaluated, jute - rice - groundnut used the max-